

Sample selected in the experiment described in the paper “Automated Data Extraction in Software Engineering SLRs: Promise, Pitfalls, and the Role of Human Oversight”

Note: The number preceding each reference corresponds to the complete list of papers considered in the SLR (222 papers). This numbering is also included in the ‘paper_id’ field of the CSV file called data_dump, which is also included in the supplementary material.

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